

PROCEDIN

Building Procurement Capability for Embedding and Driving Innovation

D5.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities

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Abstract:	This Deliverable, D7.1, presents the PROCEDIN Dissemination and Communication Plan – a comprehensive and constantly updated plan for disseminating, communicating, and utilising the project's results. It details the tools, channels, and activities that will be implemented throughout the project to ensure a successful and consistent representation of the PROCEDIN Project and its outcomes.

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PROCEDIN

Procurement Capability - Embedding and Driving Innovation

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
CA	Consortium Agreement
CE	Circular Economy
DC	Dissemination and Communication
DC-KPI	Dissemination and Communication Key Performance Indicator
DCO	Dissemination and Communication Objectives
DGP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GM	Green Mobility
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
POI	Procurement of Innovation
WP	Work Package

1 Summary

In this deliverable, D5.1, the PROCEDIN Project presents its Plan for Dissemination, Communication and Activities (DCP), which is a dynamic and comprehensive document detailing the tools, channels and activities that will be utilised throughout the project to ensure effective and consistent visual representation of the PROCEDIN Project, as well as its activities and outcomes, for successful dissemination of results. The DCP outlines the strategy, activities and tools that will be used to communicate with stakeholders at different stages of the project. This deliverable is important in terms of the marketing success of the project and represents the link between dissemination and communication activities in other Work Packages (WPs). The set of rules and standards presented in the DCP will guide PROCEDIN partners towards effective communication with target audiences from the outset of the project.

The DCP also distinguishes between communication and dissemination activities. **Dissemination activities** involve the public disclosure of project results with the objective of transferring knowledge and outcomes to targeted stakeholders. **Communication activities**, on the other hand, involve strategic and targeted measures to inform and promote project activities, actions, and results to diverse audiences, showcasing the impact and benefits of the European Union (EU)-funded project.

This deliverable consists of the following sections:

- **Chapter 1:** This chapter summarises the aim of this deliverable and provides an overview of this document.
- **Chapter 2:** The second chapter provides a brief introduction to the PROCEDIN project and its main objectives.
- **Chapter 3:** This chapter introduces the main objectives of dissemination and communication activities as well as the methodology and approach used in designing the Dissemination and Communication Plan. Finally, this chapter paints an accurate picture of the PROCEDIN target audiences and crafts the narrative and key messages to be delivered.
- **Chapter 4:** The fourth chapter offers an overview of the PROCEDIN Dissemination Strategy and presents expected outputs to be disseminated and the engagement strategy.
- **Chapter 5:** In this chapter, the PROCEDIN Communication Strategy is presented with a detailed description of the project visual identity and the channels and tools to be used. It also details on networking and liaison activities with other initiatives.
- **Chapter 6:** This chapter reflects on the importance of this document and upcoming activities.

The present PROCEDIN deliverable – prepared within the Dissemination and Communication Work Package (WP5) – will ensure that all communication and dissemination needs from various WPs and the project, in general, are considered and coordinated.

The strategy and plan of dissemination and communication will be continually monitored, updated (by M18) and reported during the project.

2 PROCEDIN Project Introduction

The adoption of (public) procurement of innovation (POI) practices – which bring together business and public sectors – relies on legal reforms, European, national and regional policies, growing

expertise, guidance, tools and case studies, and networks of early adopters. However, to drive deep, systemic change, the rate, scale, and scope of POI adoption must increase.

To accelerate POI in the specific domains of Circular Economy (CE) and Green Mobility (GM), in the context of European cities' innovation for sustainability and resilience agendas, this project will leverage existing resources and its members' pan-European professional networks, and initiate new provisions to enhance and mobilise POI motivation, knowledge, and skills.

The complex landscape of growing expertise, experience, and learning infrastructure will be mapped, and resources will be related to the varied needs of different stakeholder archetypes (defined by organisation type, extent of POI experience, etc.) to identify and address key gaps in provision. Special attention will be given to promoting enduring access to, and increased uptake of, POI guidance and learning resources for buyers and vendors, and building leadership capacity for driving and embedding innovation through strategic procurement.

2.1 PROCEDIN Project Objectives

Collectively, encouraging POI capability development and accelerating the growth of CE and GM innovation ecosystems are essential components to meet European Green Deal goals and priorities for societal resilience. The following **PROCEDIN's objectives** are carefully crafted with that in mind:

- 01.** To map, make more accessible, and promote the use of, POI development resources.
- 02.** To map and mobilise key POI stakeholders to accelerate and embed POI adoption.
- 03.** To develop, provide and promote uptake of guidance on legal frameworks.
- 04.** To facilitate procurement leadership in driving and embedding POI to generate dynamic innovation ecosystems.
- 05.** To disseminate project activities, resources and other outcomes throughout the duration of the project, via multiple channels to reach all stakeholder groups.

This deliverable with focus in more detail into all the activities that will support the **objective 05**, as it concerns making a wide range of resources – covering more technical/procedural and ‘soft skills’ for cooperation and leadership – widely accessible, encouraging uptake through direct and systemic measures. Furthermore, it will highly support **objective 04**, as dissemination and communication activities address system-level development through procurement leadership.

This Deliverable has a core **link to seven other deliverables** related to engagement, ecosystem development, dissemination, communication and impact: D2.1 Accessible map of ecosystems, reporting on clusters' needs, capabilities and barriers to POI; D2.2 Engagement plan; D3.2 In person trainings and recorded legal trainings including legal framework and best practices; D3.3 Best practice compilation with navigation decision interface; D4.3 Engagement opportunities guidance with event; D5.2 Report on ecosystem building and impact; D5.3 Exploitation, replicability and sustainability (ER&S) Plan) and therefore links to **Milestones 2 to 9**.

3 Dissemination and Communication Plan

Dissemination and Communication (DC) of project results are one of the key activities to maximise their impact. The PROCEDIN dissemination and communication plan serves as a practical tool for

efficiently developing and implementing dissemination activities with the overall objective of contributing to achieve the project expected impacts. The goal is to maximise the project impact by **facilitating use of POI resources** and other learning/training interventions among the targeted stakeholder groups. The aim is to create an environment where a stakeholder is i) knowing that the resource exists; ii) being able to access a relevant resource at the right time; iii) motivation based on perceived value.

The following are the focus points related to the communication of the benefits of the PROCEDIN results:

- I. Identifying and organising the activities necessary for communicating the benefits of the PROCEDIN outputs and their positive impacts.
- II. Communicating and disseminating the project's innovative results.
- III. Raising citizens' awareness of the project's impacts on relevant policy areas and promoting the PROCEDIN results within the ecosystem.

Although dissemination and communication activities are complementary processes, they may overlap among audiences and communication channels. Acknowledging this aspect, this document will discuss Dissemination and Communication separately.

The aim of these activities is to increase public awareness of the PROCEDIN project's activities and to publicly disclose its results within Europe and internationally. Additionally, the DCP is considered a crucial element in attracting the target audience's interest and encouraging them to adopt the PROCEDIN results. To achieve this, the consortium members will capitalise on existing communication channels (e.g., those of their institutions) and their own reputation to raise awareness and promote new and unforeseen interactions with potential end-users.

3.1 Objectives of Dissemination and Communication Activities

The dissemination and communication strategies of PROCEDIN are closely aligned with the project's objectives and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (Table 7). To ensure adherence to these objectives and KPIs, particularly with regards to stakeholder engagement and exploitation activities, the DCP is designed to promote PROCEDIN and its accomplishments, while also engaging a broad audience and potential users by addressing their key concerns. The specific goals of the dissemination and communication efforts (DCO) are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. PROCEDIN Dissemination Objectives

DCO1	Raise awareness among the key sectors dealt by the project on the PROCEDIN's mission to encourage the Procurement of Innovation capability development;
DCO2	Ensure decision-makers are informed about the project, inciting policy related uptake and spill over;
DCO3	Foster synergies with other initiatives, capitalising on existing dissemination channels and networks to ensure efficient communication and understanding of PROCEDIN offerings;
DCO4	Introduce new patterns of conduct in the target groups and end-users of the project results and build networks of early adopters to start generating market demand for the PROCEDIN solutions and technologies; and
DCO5	Support the exploitation strategy by attracting potential users for the post-project market deployment of PROCEDIN offerings.

These specific dissemination and communication objectives have been defined to influence behaviour, develop opinion and to raise awareness of specific target groups, following these steps: **Why** – purpose of the DC action; **What** – the message/content that will be disseminated and communicated; **To whom** – the target audience; **How** – the method of dissemination and communication; **When** – the timing of the DC activities.

Dissemination and communication represent horizontal activities and concentrate on disseminating the results of the PROCEDIN project itself to a wide range of existing and/or potential audiences. The practical experience and guidance that will emerge from the project work will be of relevance to an array of stakeholders within the EC and beyond and will be of value across different sectors and internationally. Clear channels of communications between the project partners themselves as well as with a broader community will play a crucial role in the success of the project.

3.2 Methodology and Approach

The PROCEDIN DCP is developed collaboratively among consortium members to engage stakeholders (as identified in WP2) and increase the reach of outputs and knowledge generated by the project. The plan prioritises simplicity and consistency in communication, tailored to the specific needs of the target audience. Understanding user requirements and stakeholder features is critical to developing effective dissemination and communication strategies, ensuring that messages are delivered through appropriate channels. The approach involves outlining key activities and dependencies to maximise the effectiveness of the PROCEDIN, as listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Key Activities & Critical Questions

Activity	Critical Questions	Chapter
Targeting	Who is our target audience? What is our message?	3
Methods	How are we going to reach that audience?	3 and 4
Content Development	What types of content does our audience find engaging? What outputs, results and activities can PROCEDIN offer?	5
Timing	When is the right time to reach our target audience?	5
Evaluation	How effective are our public outreach efforts?	5

The PROCEDIN strategy for dissemination and communication will be a setup of activities classified on three different levels, depending on the type of action:

Dissemination for awareness is aimed at the general public and to those stakeholders that should be aware of the work of PROCEDIN, but do not require a detailed knowledge of the project.

Dissemination for understanding targets specific audiences and those stakeholders that may benefit from PROCEDIN results but are not directly involved in the project such as universities and research institutes, corporations as well as small- and medium-sized enterprises (SME).

Dissemination for action refers to a change of practice resulting from the adoption of the knowledge generated. The specific audience here will be stakeholders to be clearly identified among the POI community, as well as policymakers and institutions in a position to influence and bring about change within their organisations and/or relevant sectors as well as to advocate for the exploitation of the PROCEDIN solutions.

To achieve more meaningful and worthwhile interactions with different target audiences, a set of general principles has been adopted and oriented towards the long-term sustainability of the project:

Long-term relationship building and raising confidence and trust. PROCEDIN will build respect and recognition, as well as cultivate trust in its ecosystem by leveraging sector-specific expertise and experience to market - the PROCEDIN offerings to the target audiences.

Individualised and multi-channel communication. PROCEDIN will enhance interactions and foster closer links with its targeted audiences by delivering relevant and personalised messages, across various topics important to identified ecosystem stakeholders.

The PROCEDIN places a significant emphasis on **addressing gender issues** and ensuring language accessibility in accordance with established standards for gender and generation inclusivity. To avoid gender stereotypes, the communication materials and activities of PROCEDIN utilise proactive and inclusive language, including selecting images featuring women in active roles on the project website and other communication channels. Additionally, the DC team of PROCEDIN strives to avoid technical language and terminology wherever possible to increase the accessibility of project results to a broader audience.

3.3 PROCEDIN Ecosystem of Stakeholders

The success of the PROCEDIN depends not only on the deployment of its results, but also on its impact on relevant stakeholders. These stakeholders are defined as individuals or groups who have an interest in or are affected by the project. To effectively communicate and disseminate information, it is essential to first identify and classify target stakeholders within WP2. This enables the selection of appropriate messages, communication tools and channels. It is also important to analyse the power structure among stakeholders to prioritize outreach efforts and account for shifting dynamics.

3.3.1 Target Groups and Key Messages

The PROCEDIN project has identified **nine target groups** that it aims to engage and communicate with effectively. These include **i)** vendor firms, especially SMEs and high-tech start-ups, **ii)** public procurement professionals aspiring to leadership roles, **iii)** public contracting authorities in urban areas, **iv)** procurement professional associations, **v)** anchor institutions (PCA neighbours) and large firms in PCAs' supply chains, and other large private buyers (potentially) implementing POI practices. The project also targets **vi)** innovation policy leads, particularly those related to innovation ecosystem development, **vii)** Horizon projects and other EU initiatives (e.g., Procurement Professionalisation), **viii)** business development policy leads, especially those related to eco-transitions (notably CE and GM related), and **ix)** university educators specialising in strategic procurement, entrepreneurship, sustainability, and researchers. The success of PROCEDIN's communication and engagement efforts will depend on understanding the needs and characteristics of each target group and using appropriate communication channels to deliver the right messages.

Table 3 defines the key audience profiles for the PROCEDIN, grouped into three target groups, along with the expected impact of communication activities.

Table 3. Main PROCEDIN Stakeholder Groups and Expected Impacts of DC Activities

Level	Target Group	Target Audience Profiles (TO WHOM)	Expected Impacts (WHY)
Dissemination for Awareness	General audience (GA)	General Public: European citizens & stakeholders at large. Related Horizon projects & Other EU initiatives (e.g., Procurement Professionalisation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness about the project, objectives, results and impact; - Greater and more meaningful engagement in policy making; - Increased understanding of the POI and how to make better informed and more sustainable choices.
Dissemination for Understanding/Uptake	External audience directly related to the project results (EA)	<p>Public procurement professionals, especially those in or aspiring to leadership roles</p> <p>Regulation community, policy makers, admin. European Commission, National governments, National decision-makers; Business development policy leads, especially related eco-transitions (notably CE and GM related)</p> <p>University educators (strategic procurement, entrepreneurship, sustainability), and researchers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aggregation and classification of existing scientific knowledge - New knowledge and empirical open data on the application of novel inclusive POI practices; - Create media interest to get their involvement and support; - Stimulate and support further research; - Improved, more inclusive and better-informed governance models based on stakeholder engagement; - Insights into local peculiarities and potentialities along with the means to tap into POI
Dissemination for Action	Audience in connection with the project (PA)	Vendor firms, especially SMEs and high-tech start-ups; Anchor institutions (PCA neighbours) and large firms in PCAs' supply chains, and other large private buyers (potentially) implementing POI practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Networking and stakeholder engagement to build connections required to accelerate innovation; - Increased awareness of new business opportunities and its benefits building demand for innovative products/services.

Broad concepts of the key messages have been defined per target group, highlighting the advantages provided by PROCEDIN and are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. PROCEDIN Key Messages

Target Group	Key Messages (WHAT)	Tools and Channels (HOW)
General audience (GA)	<p>Civil Society & Consumers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased socio-economic and environmental benefits from policies; - More sustainable, healthy and affordable 	Website, flyers, videos, newsletters, interviews and featured articles, success stories, social media, media

	products and services.	pack (for journalists), Actionable Knowledge stemming from all WPs (such as factsheets, infographics, etc.) to maximise the impact of the project and the awareness of the community and to the wider public.
External audience directly related to the project results (EA)	Researchers & academia: - Advance research in focal scientific fields in the POI domain - Keep up to date with industry and policy developments on the field	Website, flyers, videos, newsletters, interviews and featured articles, success stories, social media, events, scientific publications
Audience in connection with the project (PA)	Public (and private) buyers of innovation: - Better informed and effective policies for implementing POI. Progress towards meeting regional, national and EU policy targets. Introduction of socio-economic and environmental benefits in their ecosystem. Vendors (SMEs) advisors & investors: - Increased market penetration of innovations. Development of innovative value chains delivering sustainable products/ services. Capitalise on emerging investment opportunities in CE	Website, flyers, videos, newsletters, interviews and featured articles, success stories, social media, events, scientific publications

3.4 Dissemination and Communication Procedures

The involvement of any partner in organised internal or external events or any dissemination activities related to the PROCEDIN project, must be internally reported, reviewed and approved by the PROCEDIN Project WP5 Leader (F6S). If dissemination activities include the project results protected through Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), review and approval of the PROCEDIN IPR manager will be required.

The DC procedure has been set up to:

- I. Produce high-quality PROCEDIN publications and presentations;
- II. Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information; and
- III. Monitor and record the dissemination activities of the project appropriately.

Reporting: Any partner planning to participate in internal or external events or any DC activities related to the PROCEDIN project must first report their intention to the PROCEDIN Project WP5 Leader. This report should include the nature of the event or activity, the target audience, the proposed content, and any other relevant details.

Review: WP5 Leader F6S will review the report and assess whether the proposed activity aligns with the project objectives and overall communication and dissemination strategy. The review will also ensure that there are no overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information.

Approval: If the proposed activity is deemed appropriate, F6S will approve it. However, if the proposed DC activities include the project results protected through Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), review and approval of the PROCEDIN IPR manager will be required.

Production: Once approved, the partner can proceed with producing the publication or presentation for the proposed activity. The production should meet the project's high-quality standards, including adherence to the project's communication and dissemination guidelines. If the proposed activity is an event, partners will be provided with a step-by-step detailed plan event organisation (planning, promotion, during the event, post-event). This plan is available in the internal repository and serves as a guide to ensure that all partners are aligned and consistent in their dissemination efforts for the event.

Dissemination: The partner can then disseminate the publication or presentation as planned, ensuring that it reaches the target audience effectively.

Monitoring and recording: WP5 Leader will monitor and record the DC activities of the project appropriately. This will help to evaluate the impact of the dissemination activities and ensure that the project is meeting its communication and dissemination objectives.

The partners are regularly reminded about the existence of the **Event Report**, which is a form based on the continuous reporting on the project's dissemination and communication activities mandated by the European Commission. This report is distributed to all partners to ensure that they are aware of its importance and are equipped to submit it as required.

4 PROCEDIN Dissemination Strategy

Effective dissemination is crucial for the success of the PROCEDIN project. The resources developed through WP2, WP3, and WP4 will not be successfully utilised unless end-users and their development supporters are aware of them and motivated to use them.

It is essential to maintain continuous engagement with stakeholders from all groups in the POI community. PROCEDIN's dissemination efforts will ensure that individuals and organisations representing all the target stakeholder groups are aware of the project's activities and the value of its outputs. Additionally, these activities will facilitate the re-use of excellent elements from the PROCEDIN project.

The dissemination of information will include several key elements. Firstly, the purpose, objectives, value, and relevance of the PROCEDIN project will be highlighted. To ensure differentiation and complementarity, attention will be paid to other initiatives in the same field, including those covered by the current call. Messages about the project will be periodically reviewed in light of project progress and external developments. Secondly, news, achievements, and results will be disseminated, and partners will showcase how PROCEDIN contributes to POI in cities. Thirdly, PROCEDIN events and publications will be organized to present the project's results, such as the report on leadership barriers and enablers from T2.4. Finally, project assets, including the resource base and learning resources, will be shared with stakeholders.

As set out in the Grant Agreement (GA), **partners are obliged to communicate and disseminate the project and its results** by disclosing them to the public, if not stated otherwise. Specific provisions for dissemination (dissemination restrictions) are set out in the GA and the Consortium Agreement (CA).

Also, while performing the dissemination activities, according to the same document, the partners are required to respect the following:

1. Open Access to Scientific Publication, where each partner who plans to publish data in the relevant scientific medium must ensure open access (i.e., free-of-charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, the partners must:
 - a. As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications. Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
 - b. Ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - i. On publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher; or
 - ii. Within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
 - c. Ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata should be in a standard format and must include all of the following:
 - i. The terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”;
 - ii. The name of the action, acronym and grant number;
 - iii. The publication date, and length of the embargo period, if applicable; and
 - iv. A persistent identifier.
2. Open access to research data (with respect to the digital research data generated in the action - “data”). In particular, the partners must:
 - a. Deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:
 - i. The data including associated metadata needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible; and
 - ii. Other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the ‘data management plan’.
 - b. Provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

The PROCEDIN Dissemination strategy follows the EU Guidelines for the successful dissemination of the HORIZON Europe project results as well as the obligation defined within the PROCEDIN Grant Agreement. By disclosing the project results, the focus of the PROCEDIN dissemination-related activities is threefold:

- To disseminate the respective project results to the audience that may take an interest in the potential use of the results (i.e., researcher community, policy makers, etc.).
- To openly demonstrate clear economic, social and environmental benefits of utilizing PROCEDIN outputs with the targeted users.

As for the target audiences of the dissemination defined in Section 3.3.1, the PROCEDIN Dissemination Strategy is focused on i) the external audience directly related to the project results and ii) the

audience in connection to the project. On the other hand, considering the defined level of the dissemination, the strategy is focused on dissemination for understanding and dissemination for action.

4.1 Dissemination Activities

Ensuring a dynamic interaction with the targeted audiences is crucial for achieving long-term impact and market uptake of the PROCEDIN project outcomes. To achieve this, PROCEDIN will leverage the strong positioning of its partners, including their participation in initiatives, clusters, and platforms, as well as their active involvement in conferences and prolific content publications, among other efforts. This will enable the project to reach and influence various target groups, with the support and coordination of the F6S as the WP5 leader. The F6S will also leverage its vast industrial network to amplify the impact of the project results. The focus of the dissemination activities in respect to the timeline of the project are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. PROCEDIN Dissemination Activities Phases

Phase	Focus
Phase I (M1–M09)	Approach-oriented content: Promotion of the project objectives, and dissemination of existing knowledge related to procurement of innovation.
Phase II (M09–M24)	Result-oriented content: project intermediate and final results. Dissemination of the results and achievements.
Post-project period	Result-oriented content: project final results. Dissemination of the results, various analyses and assessments of the project results (mainly through publications and conferences).

Each partner will focus on attracting the interest of specific target groups, and all partners are requested to plan their dissemination activities accordingly. Additionally, partners will report their achievements every two months throughout the project, as compared to their planned activities.

The main dissemination activities of the PROCEDIN project are presented in the following subchapters to ensure that all partners are aligned and consistent in their efforts to disseminate the project outcomes effectively.

4.1.1 Conferences and Events

PROCEDIN partners will actively participate in both virtual and physical international and local conferences/meetings outside of the project to disseminate the project results and raise awareness around PROCEDIN activities and achievements. Each partner will report their involvement with PROCEDIN at conferences and events that they are attending or hosting (see 3.4). The types of activities and events that partners are expected to participate in include: (i) conferences, industry events, exhibitions, and joint events with other H2020/HORIZON EU projects and (ii) workshops, courses, seminars, and training sessions.

The project partners have created a comprehensive list of relevant events related to the PROCEDIN project. This list includes various conferences, workshops, seminars, and other events that are of

relevance to the project's goals and objectives. The list is regularly updated by the partners to ensure that it remains current and relevant.

The list of events is stored in the project's internal repository, where all partners have access to it. This ensures that the partners are aware of upcoming events and can plan their involvement in them accordingly. The list of events serves as a valuable resource for the partners to identify opportunities to disseminate project outcomes and to engage with relevant stakeholders.

4.1.1.1 Project Organised Events

PROCEDIN is set to organise two events with over 25 participants each, aimed at bringing together leaders of Procurement of Innovation (POI) in buying organisations, other POI stakeholders, and universities. The objective is to promote and facilitate engagement among these groups, including civil society organisations if possible. Portions of the events will be recorded and edited, in order to produce informative extracts that can be made available with guidance to interested parties. Furthermore, GAB will coordinate the delivery of legal assistance on innovation procurement through organising four editions of 2-day training sessions on legal framework.

In the future, a **Final Event** will be held to showcase the PROCEDIN education model and its outcomes to the European Commission and other relevant stakeholders. The details of the final event will be elaborated upon in D5.2 Updated Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities, which is expected to be released in month 18 of the project timeline.

It is currently envisaged that the final event will be a joint event involving three projects that form the Innovation Procurement Task Force (PROCEDIN, BUILD, Health InnoFacilitator). This event will provide an excellent opportunity to showcase the significant achievements of PROCEDIN and the other projects, highlighting the collective impact of innovation procurement activities. The final event will serve as a platform for disseminating project outcomes and promoting the procurement of innovation across Europe.

4.1.2 Webinars, Lectures and Seminars

PROCEDIN will be organising a **series of webinars** on an ad-hoc basis, which will be used to present the project milestones and activities. These webinars will serve as an excellent platform to disseminate the project's findings, engage with stakeholders, and promote the procurement of innovation across Europe.

The webinars will cover a range of topics related to the PROCEDIN project, including:

- Overview of the project's objectives, methodology, and expected outcomes.
- Innovative procurement practices and strategies.
- Success stories from the project, highlighting best practices and lessons learned.
- The role of education and training in promoting innovative procurement practices.
- The impact of innovation procurement on the European economy and society.
- The role of public-private partnerships in innovation procurement.

The webinars will be organised by the project partners and/or in collaboration with other projects, and will feature presentations by experts in the field of innovative procurement. The webinars will be accessible to a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, procurement practitioners, academics, and industry professionals. The webinars will also be recorded and made available on the project's website, ensuring that stakeholders who are unable to attend the live event can still access the information.

4.1.3 Publications in Journals

The first submissions to journals will take place when substantial results emerge from the project. The **scientific publications** will be offered with green or gold open access, which means they will be freely available to the public either immediately upon publication (gold) or after an embargo period (green). PROCEDIN will use Open Research Europe as an open peer review venue, which will facilitate open and constructive research discussions to enhance the quality and relevance of the project's results.

To achieve early and open sharing of research, PROCEDIN will use various strategies. First, the project will preregister research studies on an appropriate platform, such as the Centre of Open Science or aspredicted.org, and share time-stamped, read-only versions of publications. Second, PROCEDIN will upload open datasets on the Zenodo repository, which will allow other researchers to access and reuse the data. By using these strategies, PROCEDIN will ensure that its research is transparent, accessible, and reproducible.

In addition to scientific publications, PROCEDIN will also publish **non-scientific reports** to present project results and outcomes to a broader audience. For instance, the leadership barriers and enablers report from T2.4 will be published as a non-scientific report with a wider dissemination plan, which includes sharing the report with relevant stakeholders, such as policy makers, practitioners, and other interested parties.

4.1.4 PROCEDIN Project Video

In the future, PROCEDIN plans to develop a one- or two-minutes **explainer video** to showcase the project and its objectives (currently due to M12). The video will highlight the main features of the project and its expected impact. It will be produced in collaboration with a professional video production company to ensure high-quality production values.

The video will be made available on the PROCEDIN website and shared via social media platforms to reach a wider audience. The video will be a valuable tool to raise awareness about the project and attract potential stakeholders and partners.

4.2 Partner Roles and Responsibilities

All **PROCEDIN partners will engage in communication and dissemination activities** at both consortium and partner levels, as an integral part of their respective Work Packages and areas of expertise. Partners will collaborate closely to identify and organise relevant activities, and work together to engage with target audiences, relevant projects and initiatives.

To maximise the impact of PROCEDIN, partners are encouraged to integrate dissemination and communication actions into all project activities, and to share success stories and good practices to create synergies with other partners and reach a wider audience. Partners are also encouraged to **actively engage with local and national media outlets** (such as press, radio, and TV), and offer interviews, visits, and demonstrations to showcase their work. F6S innovative communication team leverages this information and a strong experience in community building to deliver a high-impact strategy to promote, communicate, and disseminate research activities and achievements, maximising sustainability of projects' results.

In addition, partners can leverage existing press offices at their organizations, such as those found at universities, to help identify and contact media outlets and generate interest in the project. By working

together and proactively engaging with different audiences, PROCEDIN partners can effectively communicate the project's objectives and outcomes, and promote wider uptake and impact.

4.2.1 Partner Obligations and Public Deliverables

In accordance with the GA, partners will have the **obligation to communicate and disseminate the project** and its results to the public, adhering to specific provisions for dissemination (dissemination restrictions) outlined in both the GA and the CA.

Deliverables marked as public will be available as downloads on the project website, after receiving approval from the Management and Quality Plan (D6.1) and the European Commission. Dissemination and communication of results from deliverables classified as either confidential or restricted require approval from the consortium or the involved partners prior to release.

To ensure effective communication and dissemination of the project results, partners will have specific responsibilities, as defined below:

- All partners will dedicate efforts to communication and dissemination activities through the channels and tools outlined in the project's communication plan.
- The dissemination lead (F6S) will support partners in implementing these activities.
- All partners will be responsible for providing content related to their project activities for use in different channels, including blog posts on the project website.
- The development of the project newsletters will be the responsibility of F6S, with partners providing information and content related to their project activities.
- The management of social media networks will be the responsibility of F6S.
- All partners will be responsible for actively interacting with the project's social media networks.
- All partners will be responsible for reporting their communication and dissemination activities.

5 PROCEDIN Communication Strategy

The PROCEDIN project will continue to implement its communication strategy throughout the project duration. The strategy aims to showcase the project's impact and benefits to its target audiences. To achieve this, a funnelled approach, similar to a marketing funnel, will be adopted to ensure wide, but targeted communication. The strategy will employ a mix of communication means, including different media and activities, to reach distinct target audience groups.

A coherent approach, including a common visual identity, will be adopted to synchronize communication activities by the whole consortium. This will ensure that appropriate media and formats with a custom audience-tailored message are used, maximising the impact of the available resources during the project. The project will use easy-to-understand visual content to make ideas and benefits practically recognizable to a wide audience. This approach will help to increase the curiosity of future end-users, who will be guided to more comprehensive knowledge and resources on solutions and services.

The project will customize its material and communicate it to different target audience groups, with the aim of building and sustaining a community of engaged stakeholders. The project will collect useful knowledge from project deliverables, interactions with partners, and other target audiences, case

studies, and partner publications. This knowledge will be conveyed via PROCEDIN communication networks to help promote the project's achievements.

PROCEDIN will also engage in broad communication through the **Urban Agenda** Partnership network and during the Urban Agenda Partnership meetings. By leveraging these networks, PROCEDIN can increase its visibility and reach within the relevant communities.

5.1 PROCEDIN Channels and Tools

PROCEDIN will create and make use of main communication tools and channels including online, offline and interactive (face-to-face) ones that will be implemented by the PROCEDIN partners to achieve an efficient and effective interaction with the different stakeholders. Some resources are of general intent, whereas some are geared to particular target groups. Building on the knowledge and diverse engagement of PROCEDIN partners with their audiences, PROCEDIN will concentrate on the usage of unique communication channels that project partners successfully utilise for their day-to-day interactions with different audiences.

5.1.1 PROCEDIN Visual Identity

An integrated and consistent visual identity underpins all communication products and tools and forms the basis for a commercial brand. The visual identification (logo and style) of the project will enable external audiences to clearly perceive PROCEDIN and contribute to the awareness of the project by having a coherent identity from the very beginning of the project. All the dissemination and communication tools (project website, Twitter account and LinkedIn page), materials (presentations, posters, roll up, documents, letters, etc.) and deliverables, will employ the visual identity developed for the project, guaranteeing a professional and consistent look.

5.1.1.1 PROCEDIN Logo

The development of a visual identity and a project logo ensures project outputs are consistent and easily recognisable. F6S provided several proposals for the PROCEDIN Logo, which all partners commented and voted upon. F6S had the selected logo vectorised and presented a brand book with a clear logo concept and a colour Pantone. The PROCEDIN Logo is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PROCEDIN Logo

The selected project logo aims to promote sustainable and circular practices, therefore, it was important to have a logo that accurately represents these areas of focus. The lightbulb shape incorporated into one of the letters in the logo represents the knowledge generation and sharing that will occur throughout the project. As the project aims collate and appraise relevant existing POI learning resources, and develop new resources, the lightbulb shape also symbolises the creativity and innovation involved in these processes.

5.1.1.2 Colour Palette

In PROCEDIN, colour is a crucial visual element for effectively communicating and representing the project brand. The selection of colours (Figure 2) was inspired by the original logo and elements within the PROCEDIN ecosystem, and they represent the project at the highest level. These colours should be present in all communications to ensure a cohesive PROCEDIN image or visual story.

Figure 2. PROCEDIN Colour Palette

The **primary colour palette** consists of #208B3A (Forest Green) and #132D46 (Elephant), representing the project's commitment to creating a greener future and promoting environmental sustainability through Circular Economy and Green Mobility practices. Additionally, a few **secondary colours** were defined to provide more flexibility to the visual elements and eliminate any potential contrast issues, such as #2DC653 (Mountain Meadow), #191E29 (Mirage) and #696E79 (Nevada).

5.1.1.3 EU Funding Acknowledgement

Across all outputs of the PROCEDIN project, and accompanying the logo, a text concerning the source of the project's funding will be provided along with the European flag, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. EU Funding Acknowledgement

In addition, any dissemination of results must indicate that the:

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

5.1.1.4 Document Templates

The PROCEDIN consortium partners were provided with a Deliverable Template in Word (Figure 4) and a PowerPoint template (Figure 5) to ensure uniformity and a distinctive visual identity in all project documentation throughout its duration. These templates are accessible through the intranet file repository system. If necessary, the Communication Manager will create additional presentations to be used in project activities. To present the project or its results at internal or external events, partners are expected to use the PROCEDIN PowerPoint template. Examples of the templates are displayed in the figures below.

Figure 4. PROCEDIN Deliverable Template

Figure 5. PROCEDIN PowerPoint Template

5.1.1.5 Visuals and Graphics

Several templates and visuals (Figure 6) were prepared to present the project on social media channels. The visuals are being developed according to each channel’s needs, using the PROCEDIN visual identity. Project elements are present in every template, to maintain coherence throughout all communication efforts.

It is highly important to create strong, unique visuals that are appealing, in order to ensure that the project’s message is heard and seen throughout all the platforms.

Figure 6. Social Media Visuals Examples

5.1.2 PROCEDIN Online Presence

5.1.2.1 PROCEDIN Website

The internet is an essential information source and a vital communication channel. PROCEDIN has already **developed its website**¹ (displayed in Figure 7) **and launched the initial version during M2**. The website serves as the primary interface for engaging with the public and caters to the diverse target audiences of PROCEDIN. Users can easily navigate to their area of interest on the website, which contains crucial information about the project and will continue to be updated regularly.

Figure 7. PROCEDIN Website Landing Page

The PROCEDIN website is a crucial management tool that enhances the dissemination and communication of project activities and outcomes to stakeholders at all levels, including the general public and local citizens. F6S manages the website, and all partners contribute to updating its content. The website provides information about the project's objectives, solutions, scope, partners, and expectations, as well as downloadable promotional material, deliverables, PowerPoint presentations, and videos.

In the later phases of the project, the website will be a crucial platform for showcasing significant findings and success stories. The website's management ensures that its content remains contemporary and features up-to-date news relevant to the project's objectives.

¹ <https://procedin.eu/>

The **Privacy Policy**² together with the **Terms of Use**³ have also been included in the PROCEDIN website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

The website has direct access to social networks by clicking on the icons situated in the footer of the website. In this way, it will be easy for every user to participate when the website is visited. To achieve the most efficient **updates/changes** on the PROCEDIN website, the consortium is set to follow the **instructions** that are detailed below:

- Updates and changes requested by email: a description of the required integration/change should be given in an attached file in .docx format (not in the text of the request email);
- If the integration/change refers to documents or files to be uploaded in the public website, these must be attached to the e-mail;
- The description should contain a clear distinction of the type of the requested integration/change, specifying which part(s) of the website need(s) to be changed, providing the link(s) of the webpage(s) to be upgraded;
- The use of abbreviations should be avoided; however, if included, abbreviations must be made explicit, at least the first time they are quoted in the description of the required integration/change; and
- Events to be integrated in the Events Section must be sent with all the necessary information (date, title, location, program and link), to provide a homogeneous level of details and information content.

Given the nature and progress of the activities during the project lifetime and related information, the PROCEDIN website is to be continuously updated and populated with relevant content.

5.1.3 PROCEDIN Social Media Channels Mix

To expand its reach and establish effective two-way communication channels, PROCEDIN project aims to have a strong presence on social media channels. The project will focus on using social media channels that its partners have been using successfully to communicate with their users and stakeholders, ensuring maximum usability and exploitation. The content will be updated continuously, and partners will share posts to support the flow of news. PROCEDIN partners will use their social media channels mainly for special occasions.

PROCEDIN project aims to use various social media channels to increase visibility, share knowledge, promote results, and interact with the public, especially stakeholders involved in pilot sites. Social media will enable PROCEDIN to reach people where they are and gain important insight. The project can leverage networking and viral effects, increasing awareness considerably.

To achieve this, the project has established a LinkedIn page and a Twitter account. The team has researched relevant hashtags and already started using some, including: #InnovationProcurement, #CircularEconomy, #GreenMobility, #Sustainability.

5.1.3.1 Social Media and Other Channels

The **PROCEDIN LinkedIn Page**⁴ is used to deliver content to particular industries, companies and researchers, as it is a platform for business networking with over 433 million members. It is a space open to anyone who wants to know about PROCEDIN's outputs, opportunities, express their views,

² <https://procedin.eu/privacy-policy/>

³ <https://procedin.eu/terms-of-use/>

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/procedin/>

ask questions, and engage more deeply with the project. Posts are shared once or twice a week throughout the project, and the frequency will increase during critical phases such as events and result sharing. Content for LinkedIn will be generated by F6S and contributed by partners.

The **PROCEDIN Twitter account**⁵ will be used to provide accurate, new, and carefully selected information to all interested parties in a light and engaging manner. The content will be both meaningful and interesting, and will create a community around the topics associated with the project. This will ensure that PROCEDIN's message is delivered to the right audiences through a well-defined network and community. The frequency of posts/reposts will be two to three times per week throughout the project, increasing during critical phases such as events and results sharing. Content creation will be sustained by F6S as well as contributions from the partners.

PROCEDIN will utilise various channels to communicate with its audiences, including email, meetings, training events, distributing important news, sending press releases, inviting engagement, and doing presentations. Partners will target relevant online newsrooms with articles and contributions, as well as offer interviews. PROCEDIN will also target **relevant EC channels** such as newsrooms and blogs, and make contributions to the coordinated dissemination portal as part of the collaboration with other support actions.

In a more advanced phase of the project, PROCEDIN will create and maintain its own **YouTube** channel that aims to disseminate all the video material the project gathers.

5.1.3.2 Content Types

The main goal of the project's content marketing strategy is to assist the target audience in their decision-making process regarding the use of PROCEDIN outputs. To achieve this objective, various forms of content will be created as outlined in Table 6.

Table 6. PROCEDIN Types of Content

Attract	Engage	Maintain	Galvanise
Educational content about the project scope and objectives, partners' presentations, partners' testimonials	Blog posts, articles, success stories, case studies, Interviews and showcase of results and key findings	Email marketing, social ads and retargeting initiatives	Events, training sessions, workshops, conferences, etc.

5.1.4 Innovation Procurement Task Force Newsletter

The PROCEDIN project is currently in communication with **the BUILD and Health InnoFacilitator projects**, all funded under HORIZON-EIE-2021-CONNECT-01-02, to explore the possibility of collaborating on a joint newsletter.

Having a joint newsletter representing the **Innovation Procurement Task Force** (see 5.2.1) would bring several benefits. The goal of having a joint newsletter is to increase the reach and impact of the three projects. By pooling together subscribers from 3 projects, the joint newsletter would reach a wider audience, enabling both projects to disseminate their messages to more people.

⁵ <https://twitter.com/procedin>

Furthermore, having one newsletter with all the related content instead of two separate newsletters would reduce the risk of audience saturation. This means that readers would be more likely to read and engage with the newsletter if it contains all the relevant information from both projects in one place.

If the joint newsletter is deemed feasible, a combined visual identity would need to be created to ensure that the newsletter represents all three projects equally. This would involve designing a visual look for the newsletter that reflects all three projects' branding and messaging.

Newsletter will be managed by PROCEDIN, and released more or less every 3 months (starting with M7, M9, M12, M18, M21, M24). These will be carefully designed to be appealing and engaging, maximising their reach, and assuring that the opening rate is high, and the bouncing rate is low.

Website visitors of all three projects may subscribe to the project's newsletter (Figure 8). Anyone will also be able to unsubscribe at any given point from the Newsletter (through a link provided in each issue of the newsletter) and all the collected data will be stored and saved in accordance with the GDPR compliance. This data will not be accessible to other third parties.

To stay engaged and competitive in interactions, PROCEDIN and project partners will take into account the following:

- Responsive email design for better engagement: Mailchimp, a real-time e-mail marketing automation platform will be used to design and distribute responsive, targeted e-mail campaigns, with the enhanced reading experience. Additionally, the platform will facilitate reporting and analytics.
- Dynamic customisation and personalisation: The e-mail double opt-in form on all three projects' website will require only an email address.

Figure 8. Innovation Procurement Task Force Newsletter Subscription Form

The newsletters created by the Innovation Procurement Task Force will be disseminated through multiple channels to ensure maximum reach and engagement. They will be shared with subscribers via email and posted on various social media platforms. In addition, an archive of all the newsletters will be available on the website's news section to enable easy access for interested parties.

To further expand the audience and encourage stakeholder engagement, Innovation Procurement Task Force partners will be urged to share the newsletters with their own networks of contacts. This will help to ensure that the valuable information contained in the newsletters reaches as many people as possible and generates interest and discussion around projects.

5.1.5 PROCEDIN Promotional Material

5.1.5.1 Mass Media Communication and Press Releases

The PROCEDIN project will produce **press releases to communicate relevant news** and updates to regional, national, and European electronic media. The targeted media platforms and journals will include those in the procurement of innovation communities. Partners will be encouraged to distribute the press releases to media within their regions and countries, as well as to their professional networks and websites. The first two press release (on project kick-off, and resource mapping) have already been published, and a continuous cooperation with press and media will be promoted by all PROCEDIN partners.

To reach a wider audience, local, regional, and national newspapers, journals, and magazines covering procurement of innovation will also be utilised to inform readers about PROCEDIN project objectives, activities, and achievements. The information will be written in the national language of each partner in a scientific jargon-free style, allowing the respective audience to understand the project's objectives and benefits. All press releases will be available on the PROCEDIN project website under the Media Section.

5.1.5.2 Printed Materials

Figure 9. PROCEDIN Leaflet

PROCEDIN will develop various promotional materials in print and digital form to effectively reach out to its target audience. The project recognizes the **environmental impact of printed materials and encourages partners to share digital versions whenever possible.**

An A3 info poster in English has already been designed to explain how PROCEDIN's target groups can benefit from its solutions and services, as well as an adapted A5 Leaflet (Figure 9). The poster can be translated into other languages while keeping the message as close as possible to the original text. An editable file is available on the project's intranet file repository system.

In addition to the info poster, PROCEDIN may also produce other materials like postcards, stickers, folders, notebooks, and t-shirts upon request. These materials will be distributed at relevant events and printed by partners locally using the recommended layout and design suggestions to maintain consistency.

PROCEDIN will also design a roll-up banner stand for display at its events and other external events related to the project. A 1-pager flyer will also be produced until M12 to explain the concepts of PROCEDIN, which will be updated by the end of the project to showcase the outcomes and results.

As the project matures, more attractive and comprehensive materials like reports, factsheets, policy briefs, posters, and exhibition materials may be created to further disseminate the project's results and outcomes.

5.2 Networking and Liaison with Other Initiatives

PROCEDIN project partners will use networking and informal personal meetings to disseminate the project's activities and outputs beyond their involved territories. In addition, official PROCEDIN presentations will be used whenever possible to present the project results and activities at different stages of project development.

PROCEDIN will actively promote its activities and gather regular information and news related to procurement of innovation by monitoring and collaborating with relevant online media blogs, news portals, publications and other media outlets. The project will also establish close ties with other relevant initiatives under EU-funded, international or national programmes to achieve higher awareness and impact on the target groups (Task 5.2).

To further support this purpose, PROCEDIN partners will consider participating in each other's events and organising common events. Close linkages will be established on both centralised and decentralised project levels to enhance collaboration and cooperation between partners. This will enable the project to reach a wider audience and maximise its impact in the scientific and engineering communities.

Aside from the world-class platforms provided by F6S and PEDAL, the consortium partners have active involvement in several established networks that they can fully utilize. Specifically, HAA, GAB, and UT are members of the **Urban Agenda Partnership⁶ for Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement (IRPP)**, with HAA as the coordinating member.

5.2.1 Innovation Procurement Task Force

PROCEDIN, BUILD⁷ and Health InnoFacilitator⁸ projects have launched the Innovation Procurement Task Force, a collaborative initiative aimed at **supporting procurement in innovative areas** such as the circular economy, green mobility, and healthcare. The task force is comprised of three EU-funded projects, each with a unique focus and approach to innovation procurement.

The Innovation Procurement Task Force is important because it provides a platform for cities, businesses, and organisations to collaborate and drive progress in innovative areas. By working together, these entities can leverage each other's strengths and expertise, ultimately leading to more sustainable and resilient communities. The EU-funded projects that form the task force play a critical role in fostering innovation procurement and helping to realise these important goals.

In addition to the individual initiatives of each project, the Innovation Procurement Task Force will also collaborate on **joint activities and communications**. This includes the creation of a **joint newsletter** (see 5.1.4) to share updates, best practices, and success stories in the area of innovation procurement. The newsletter will be a valuable resource for all stakeholders looking to learn more about the latest developments in this field.

Joint activities will be an integral part of the task force, with each project working together to organise workshops, webinars, and other events aimed at promoting innovation procurement. These activities will provide opportunities for participants to network, exchange ideas, and learn from one another, furthering the goals of the task force and advancing the field of innovation procurement.

⁶ <https://www.urbanagenda.urban-initiative.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.build-procurement.eu/>

⁸ <http://www.innofacilitator.eu/>

5.3 Timeline of Communication and Dissemination Activities

Communication and dissemination activities are planned in accordance with the stage of development in the project. Although a number of communication actions will take place during the first half of the project, the most significant dissemination activities will take place as intermediate and final research outputs are available. The dissemination will follow the **AIDA model**:

- Awareness to attract the attention of the target audience;
- Interest of the target audience;
- Desire of the target audience to know more about the project; and
- Action to lead the target audience toward

According to this principle, three phases are considered:

- **Initial phase (Awareness):** focused on increasing the visibility of the project and mobilising stakeholders and multipliers. At this phase, the main activities will be related to the implementation of the communication/dissemination tools (website, social networks and visual identity), preparation of dissemination material, general presentations of the PROCEDIN project, the distribution of publishable abstracts and progress resumes.
- **Intermediate phase (Interest/Desire):** focused on disseminating available initial data and results. Each partner will contribute at specific levels according to their expertise and technical activities focused on informing and engaging the target stakeholders when preliminary results become available. The project results and their future applications will be presented in journals and conferences to specialise the audience with the objective of stimulating the interaction with the POI community and determining the expectations of the stakeholders.
- **Final phase (Action):** focused on encouraging further exploitation of the PROCEDIN outcomes (transfer to sectors other than CE and GM, market of new products, replicability). At this phase, the results of the validation of the PROCEDIN approach and the transferability analysis will be presented in journals, conferences and relevant events.

The general timeframe of the PROCEDIN CDP in relation to the project objectives, impacts as well as implementation and exploitation activities are presented in Figure 10. As can be seen, the dissemination activities are envisioned as an ongoing dialogue with the potential PROCEDIN result users during both the project and the period after the project is finished. Logically, the dissemination activities are more weighted towards the second half of the project as the first outcome of the PROCEDIN results is being developed and tested. On the other hand, communication activities follow the timeframe of the project – from the M1 to M24.

Figure 10. Gantt Frequency of PROCEDIN Dissemination and Communication Activities

5.4 Monitoring of Communication and Dissemination Activities

Monitoring is the continuous and systematic process carried out during the project, which will generate data on the implementation. To achieve the successful implementation of Dissemination and

Communication activities, and fulfilment of the relevant objectives, a systematic monitoring will be carried out throughout the project implementation.

The impact of the PROCEDIN communication activities will be monitored on an ongoing basis and reported in the relevant deliverables (D5.2 Updated Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities – M18; and partially in D5.3 Report on ecosystem building and impact report – M24).

The monitoring system (Table 7) will provide evidence on whether the PROCEDIN Dissemination and Communication Plan is being implemented as initially planned and scheduled.

It will also address possible implementation problems and identify whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met. Emphasis is given on the pre-assessment of information needs, on the monitoring frequency and the method of collecting evidence.

Table 7. Dissemination and Communication KPIs

DC-KPI #	Key Performance Indicators Description	Indicator
DC-KPI 1	Number of presentations at events linked to the established network	>3
DC-KPI 2	Number of presentations at events hosted by contacts made during the project	>2
DC-KPI 3	Number of website visits/downloads per day after year 2	25
DC-KPI 4	Period (in months) of sustained web presence after project completion	18
DC-KPI 5	Number of participations at online and in-person events	2+2
DC-KPI 6	LinkedIn account launched and active for (at least) the duration of the project	M3
DC-KPI 7	Number of social media posts per month	5
DC-KPI 8	Number of developed videos about PROCEDIN	1
DC-KPI 9	Number of press releases	6
DC-KPI 10	Each partner disseminates the press release locally to their collaborators and networks	5x6
DC-KPI 11	Number of white papers published online and widely promoted	1
DC-KPI 12	Number of academic articles	1
DC-KPI 13	Number of legal framework trainings, in person and delivered online, including best practices	4
DC-KPI 14	Number of workshops, in person or online, for SMEs and start-ups	1
DC-KPI 15	Number of edited versions of online sessions posted to the website	5
DC-KPI 16	number of stakeholders reached and engaged during PROCEDIN via dissemination and communication activities as well as events	500

6 Conclusion and Next Steps

This deliverable (D5.1) presents the PROCEDIN dissemination and communication plan, which is a comprehensive and dynamic document that outlines the methods, channels, and activities to be implemented during the project to ensure broad acceptance and sustainability of the PROCEDIN Project.

The document provides a detailed description of the strategy, tools, and activities that will be used to communicate with different stakeholders, along with the timing of each activity throughout the project's lifespan. The Consortium suggests that this document will be reviewed periodically to ensure that it includes the most current information and opportunities for disseminating and communicating project updates.

As the project progresses, the strategies and methods outlined in the dissemination plan will be evaluated, and updates will be made as necessary. Since the project is in its early stages, the dissemination plan will be considered a living document that will go through multiple iterations as new dissemination opportunities arise. This means that the dissemination plan will evolve over time, especially with the discovery of new events and opportunities suitable for disseminating information about the project.

The impact of the PROCEDIN communication activities will be monitored on an ongoing basis and reported in the upcoming relevant deliverable, D5.2 Updated Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities, that is due M18.